

The Nationalism and National Unity

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Abstract:- Nationalism is an auto sense of national awareness on promotion of its culture, social norms, rules and regulations which are completely obeyed by the national citizens as well as the international concerns. Nationalism promotes the self- respect, identity of the citizen of the nation for the development. Unity strengthens the nation. The nationalism is the belief that the related country is superior or over the top without doubt. On the other side Nationalism balances the international relations among the countries all over the world as a best friend, sometimes there are lagging occurred due to various issues which must balance as to and fro dignity based treaties or check and balanced ideologies. As we question that what Nationalism is; it means local government, etc. Obligations outweigh other's interests who may be individual or groups. We can take some examples of Nationalism that are: intolerance, isolationism, enacting anti-immigrant policies and so on.

Keywords:- Citizenship, Sovereign Power, Auto Rights, Balanced Securities, Geopolitics.

I. INTRODUCTION

The word Nationalism auto shows that the rights as well opportunities which must be distributed among the people and they are free to feel that they are feeling with their rights and opportunities in a proper way which are governed by the local- governments, state governments or central government. Nationalism is a political, social, and economic system which is characterized by the interest of a nation or the related group. A national unity government of national unity or union government is a broad coalition government consisting all parties. Nationalism is a sense of national consciousness exalting one nation above all others and placing on promotion of its culture and interests as opposed to those other nations.

Nationalism is an ideology that holds that a nation is the fundamental unit for social life, and takes precedence over any other social and political principles. Nationalism typically makes certain claims based upon this belief. The claim that the nation is the only fully legitimate basis for a state, that each nation is entitled to its own state, and that the borders of the state should be congruent with the borders of the nation. Nationalism refers to both a political doctrine and any collective action by political and social movements on behalf of specific nations. Since the nation-state has become the dominant form of state organization. Most of the world's population now lives in states which are, at least nominally, nation-states. Historians also use the term "nationalism" to refer to this historical transition, and to the

emergence of nationalist ideology and movements. Nationalism is a form of universalism when it makes universal claims about how the world should be organized, but it is particularistic with regard to individual nations. The combination of both is characteristic for the ideology, for instance in these assertions. The starting point of nationalism is the existence of nations, which it takes as a given. Nations are typically seen as entities with a long history: most nationalists do not believe a nation can be created artificially. Nationalist movements see themselves as the representative of an existing, centuries-old nation. However, some theories of nationalism imply the reverse order - that the nationalist movements created the sense of national identity, and then a political unit corresponding to it, or that an existing state promoted a 'national' identity for itself.

➤ *Feelings as with Mother*

The Nationalism is a sensitivity which As we know that mother word shows the over the top [OTT] position and nobody can replace the position of the mother from her position because the power belongs to the mother is not to compare not to divide but we can feel the same sensitivities of love, rights as well as opportunities from many more resources and we means the citizens of the related nations are always happy as they are in their own sweet home, and these type of feelings forces to the citizens of the nation to involve in their developments towards various departments and areas as their abilities as their skills. Thus the nationalism works in the fields of good governance as well as in the fields of the best developments in which the citizens from various skills comes in front to share or involve in the improvements. Hence it is too vital for any of the countries all over the world.

II. FINDINGS

Nationalism is the belief that your own country is better than all others. Sometimes *nationalism* makes people not want to work with other countries to solve shared problems. It is important not to confuse nationalism with patriotism. Patriotism is a healthy pride in your country that brings about feelings of loyalty and a desire to help other citizens. Nationalism is the belief that your country is superior, without question or doubt. In some cases, nationalism can inspire people to break free of a foreign oppressor.

It is actually people's feelings for their nation as superior to all other nations. The concept of nationalism developed at the time of the Independence movement. National unity is a situation whereby people of diverse cultures, religions, language, political, social and economic

systems are brought together to have a common goal. The people have mutual understanding, love, co-operation and trust among themselves. We can maintain our nationality as we maintain culture, unity, diversity, each and every social discipline all over the societies; this empowers those conditions as well as the surrounding environment in such a way in which all the people can play similar role for the country for the central, regional as well as the local development. This is one of the most important factors in promoting national integration.

➤ *The Respect All Around*

The support to promote national integrity, Education, social and cultural unity, equality among people also helps to teach the feeling of national integration.

• *As we Put the Unity in Community:*

- ✓ Get To Know the People in our Community.
- ✓ Getting to know our neighbors goes a long way »when recognizing where there is a suspicious person in the area.
- ✓ Keep our Neighbors Informed.
- ✓ Get our Kids Acquainted with the Community.
- ✓ Host a Balanced Party.
- ✓ Get Involved in our Community.

• *10 Ways you can Create Peace and Unity this Season:*

- ✓ Help the Neighbor.
- ✓ Avoid Subway Drama.
- ✓ Lend a Helping Hand.
- ✓ End the Bullying.
- ✓ Show Compassion.
- ✓ Open your Mind to New Ideas.
- ✓ Let it Go, etc.

Modern nation state is still, as it was in olden times, the administrative arm of an elite ruling class or classes. This is so whether in dictatorships or democracies. The purpose of the state is to facilitate the maintenance of order at home and wage war abroad.

In modern times ruling elite is the collective capitalist class. The State, which exists where society is divided into an owning class and a property less class, and is a coercive institution through control of which the dominant class imposes its will on the subject class, would lose its function when society ceases to be divided into classes. To seek national unity is to coerce, ideologically reinforcing by calls to 'patriotism' and other such nonsense or clubbing into submission, a majority of wage enslaved citizens into accepting a status quo which maintains and reinforces their inequality in relation to the dominant parasitic economic social class which profit from the arrangement of 90-95% wealth producing workers and 5-10% owning classes.

III. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

'Nation cannot be built overnight' but for Nepal - development cannot wait to progress piece by piece. Thoughtful planning shall be followed by strong footstep of implementation. Nothing can be improved or changed without completely heartily participation of citizens. Political leaders are mirror of public and politicians are obliged to deliver developments for all trusts and responsibility awarded. As Nepal has not been able to gear up for economic development, we need to figure out unnoticed reasons behind. Constitutional democracy has bestowed few insights of progress in academic, tourism and industrial sectors. However, the same journey dissolved hope, progress, and opportunity together in a bucket of permanent migration, fear and confusion. In Nepal's journey of democracy, developments could not ripe in comparison to high hopes flourished, resulting into shrinking faith towards system and leadership. At this critical point of people's craze to leave village and shift to cities or leaving small cities to Kathmandu or shifting from country to other countries, Nepal is going to face deficit of major capital of development i.e. human capital. Faith needs to be restored to reinstate love and responsibility towards soil.

➤ *Nationalism*

Dictionary meaning of nationalism is identification of own nation and support for its interests, especially to the exclusion or detriment of interests of other nations. In brief, it is an ultimate love, care and responsibility. Economic nationalism is an ideology that favors country's intervention over other market mechanisms, with policies such as domestic control of the economy, labor and capital formation.

➤ *Facts*

General trend for landlocked countries like Nepal is that they trade 30 percent lesser than coastal countries. As transportation costs for landlocked countries are up to 50% higher than coastal countries, even more for mountainous country, importing goods would be discouraging, as they would cost more. Nevertheless, Nepal has always bucked these trends and is an import reliant economy where more than 40% of all its revenues come from import. The continual rise of imports throughout its history has been recorded. The binging on imports versus weak exports records its chronically widening trade deficit that is adversely affecting its development. Since the last 25 years contributing to more than 40% of the entire GDP of Nepal, trade has remained a key factor in determining its economic condition and direction. Nepal has been running an ever-widening trade deficit since 1965. In addition, infrastructure development could not take any remarkable achievements in these years. Even distribution of infrastructure is mandatory for transforming nation through prosperity. Clear vision, designs and roadmap are not in paper for nationwide for infrastructure and economy improvement.

➤ *Way Forward*

The reliance on imports also causes many other negative impacts ranging from lack of innovation and entrepreneurship, ballooning trade deficits, depleting foreign currency reserves and stifling of fast-paced economic growth. All these problems can spate Nepal. Therefore, it is imperative for Nepal to pursue effective import substitution strategies. Nepal has tried to come up with solutions of export-oriented industrialization and trade diversification to resolve such issues. They have produced ineffective outcomes as evident by ballooning imports, widening trade deficit, low global ranking and some of bold strategies.

➤ *Optimizing Gifted Potentials*

Nepal is naturally blessed country in terms of geological structure and resources. Laws to be framed protecting such resources from encroachment, misuse and interruption against purposeful use.

- Energy sector – Nepal has economically feasible capacity of more than 45000 MW of hydro energy and almost equal opportunity for solar. Nation shall bring long term policies to mobilize economy through own energy.
- Restrict fertile lands for habitation or commercial purpose. Five decades ago, Kathmandu used to be most livable in world but now deteriorated by unplanned urbanization. Not only country buried major portion of fertile land, also lost its beauty for tourism. So all fertile lands shall be utilized for agriculture only.
- Economically feasible products shall be produced within country by government investments. Import and consumption of luxury products shall be discouraged.
- Developments shall take place without harming natural and cultural environment. Various tourist attractions shall be brought into cities to attract tourist from all over the world.
- Mandatory service clause to be implied in logical manner.
- Love for self-grown food staples, own products shall be blended to culture

➤ *Revitalizing Education System of Nepal for Innovative Education*

Country has invested substantial amount in education sector. At present, we have approximately 35000 school, 3700 Higher Secondary Schools, 1400 colleges, 9 universities, and 4 medical institutions. Annual budget of Rs 170 billion is allocated for educational development. Unfortunately, development in Nepal Education Sector could not accelerate well in global competition. As a result, majority of Higher Secondary Graduates are moving gulf countries to earn basic earnings for survival, while eligible students/professionals migrate towards western countries for long-term relocation. Every year more than 63,000 students are going abroad (increasing per year) for studies with least chances of returning. Innovative education system shall be introduced so that citizen be motivated to stay in own country with dignity. Technological advancement and infrastructure development are crucial to bestow hope of opportunity, social security and opportunities.

➤ *Strategic Planning for better Infrastructure Developments*

Many ambitious projects were aborted in past, many areas were ignored blindly. Trans- Himalayan cross boarder railway to be built immediately. Nepal being at center of blooming economy and holding harmonious relationship with all the neighboring countries will reap maximum benefits by transportation connecting all the corners. Nation shall think about next 50 years and plan its resources, capital requirement, funding plan and cost-benefit analysis of all national projects. Rightful plans shall be developed to provide long-term direct benefits to project affected people.

IV. DIGITIZATION OF CURRENCY

Nepal's currency has continuously depreciated versus with which foreign trade payments are settled. This has caused a precarious depletion of Nepal's foreign currency reserves breaking central bank's 8-month minimum threshold. While currency devaluation or depreciation for an exporting economy usually make exports more competitive and augments growth, for an import-based economy like Nepal it depletes its foreign reserves and stifles growth. Crypto currency shall in system at first priority for various direct and indirect reasons.

➤ *Managing Geo Political Challenges*

Nepal has been suffocated in a cocoon made of multiple layers of geological challenges, diverse emotional barriers, national- international politics and century's old debates and limitations. Rigorous efforts are needed to visualize future, calculate risks, design needed roadmap and hike to create environment for sustainable growth.

➤ *Nationalism wave Needs to Flow in Nepal Air for Economic Transformation*

Nepal has crossed long and perilous journey of democracy in past six decades and nationalism was put to test many times. Fighting for basic rights of education and freedom in early 2000 BS to 2063 BS movement for republic system, patriotism concept has also been defined in various ways. At this fragile economic scenario, economic revolution shall begin with new definition of nationalism. Not only love, but also responsibility towards birth soil shall be germinated with all strings and knots. Every Nepali heart must realize that nations come first than anyone and anything. Policies and Planning shall be executed strictly without deviation from the spirit of constitution of Nepal.

For Nepal – Economic Nationalism can drive vision of nation building and development shall revolve with logical and sensible approach. Nepal shall develop national interests, create nationalism economy vision and exercise those economically feasible practices with strict laws. Human capital is most important factor for any country's development and enrolling every citizen whole heartily is must for micro to macro level policy changes and developments.

V. CONCLUSION

Nationalism is identification of own nation and support for its interests, especially to the exclusion or detriment of interests of other nations. In simple words, it is an ultimate love, care and responsibility towards one's motherland in a dignified and honorable way. It shows that each nation should be governed itself. While there is a strong unity among the citizens in any nation, there exists super and good governance and then after that nation turns itself towards a very good management. Including these above highlights there must be check and balance in between as well as among the neighboring countries for the better development.

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